

EVALUATIONS OF EXISTING METHODS

Ocean acidification at the crossroads I: Harmonizing unpurified and purified meta-cresol purple spectrophotometric pH_T measurements based on absorbance data

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Abstract

Consistent monitoring of seawater spectrophotometric pH on the total hydrogen ion scale (pH_T) has been questioned by an evolving method, with changes in parameterization and the purity of the meta-cresol purple (mCP). Using real seawater samples, we demonstrate that spectrophotometric pH_T measurements obtained with unpurified (UNPUR) and purified (PUR) mCP can be harmonized to within 0.003 pH units, the climate-goal threshold. This agreement is only achieved when mCP impurities at 434 nm are quantified for both the UNPUR and PUR mCP, assuming no impurities affect 545 nm absorbances, and impurity-corrected absorbance data at 434 nm are used in the same parameterization to calculate pH_T. We applied this approach to a ship-based pH_T time series transitioning from UNPUR to PUR mCP measurements. Our results show that previous claims suggesting that UNPUR mCP underestimates pH_T in the upper pH range are misleading, as they were based on the inappropriate use of absorbances obtained with UNPUR mCP with a parameterization developed for PUR mCP. In fact, our data reveal better agreement between UNPUR and PUR pH_T in the upper pH range of seawater, while UNPUR mCP tends to overestimate pH_T in the lower pH range. These findings highlight the urgent need for the global chemical oceanography community to establish a spectrophotometric pH_T method with full traceability to the International System of Units (SI), along with affordable and distributed certified reference materials and characterized purified mCP. This work supports the need for harmonization efforts to ensure the reliability of pH_T data in global synthesis products.

The pH decrease in the global ocean ascribed to the ocean absorption of anthropogenic carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions (Gruber et al. 2019; Friedlingstein et al. 2022) is

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called ocean acidification (Caldeira and Wickett 2005; Raven 2005; Doney 2009). This process has been identified as a main stressor and threat to ocean ecosystems and the human economic activities that depend on them (Turley and Gattuso 2012; Gattuso et al. 2014; Williamson and Widdicombe 2018; Doney et al. 2020). Among the four measurable variables of the seawater CO₂ system, pH would be the target for quantifying and reporting ocean acidification, and hopefully verifying the effectiveness of any mitigation efforts and/or safe CO₂ removal procedures aimed at

reducing the atmospheric CO₂ increase, and consequently in the ocean.

The Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) identified the seawater CO₂ system variables (collectively referred to as Inorganic Carbon in GOOS, and including seawater pH) as Ocean Essential Variables for monitoring and assessing the state of the ocean and its interactions with the Earth's climate system. Even more, seawater pH was recognized as a Global Climate Indicator or Essential Climate Variable by the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) (WMO 2015; Garcia-Soto et al. 2021). Major efforts to implement the observation, quality control, and reporting requirements of seawater pH data are documented by the Global Ocean Acidification Observing Network (GOA-ON) Implementation Strategy (Newton et al. 2015; Tilbrook et al. 2019). The GOA-ON climate-goal uncertainty in pH was set to 0.003 pH units, so as to detect 0.1% changes in seawater carbonate ion concentration. A more relaxed criterion was set for weather-goal pH observations (0.02 pH units). No quality criterion was set for the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) indicator 14.3.1, *Average marine acidity (pH) measured at an agreed suite of representative sampling stations*, required by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO (IOC-UNESCO 2024), although an estimate of the uncertainty should be reported in the metadata. The European Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) is trying to align ocean acidification monitoring within the Good Environmental Status assessment (Galdies et al. 2020), and the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Northeast Atlantic, or OSPAR Convention, sustains a task force on ocean acidification assessment (McGovern et al. 2022), also aligned with the Northeast Atlantic Environment Strategy (NEAES) 2030. All these efforts rely on seawater pH measurements comparable in space and time, i.e., metrologically reproducible and traceable, preferentially to the International System of Units (SI).

Historically, seawater pH was measured potentiometrically, but difficulties in referencing the measurements rendered them incomparable. Spectrophotometric methods emerged in the late 1980s to address this issue (Brewer 2013). The current reference method for seawater pH measurements is based on spectrophotometric analysis, involving the addition of a sulfonephthalein pH indicator dye, usually meta-cresol purple (mCP), to seawater samples (Byrne and Breland 1989; Clayton and Byrne 1993). These works form the foundation of the seawater pH standard operation procedure (SOP 6b—*Determination of the pH of seawater using the indicator dye m-cresol purple*; Dickson et al. 2007), which in turn largely inspired the ISO (International Organization for Standardization) 18191:2015 standard.

Spectrophotometric pH on the total hydrogen ion scale (pH_T) is calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{pH}_T = p(K_2^T e_2) + \log_{10} \left[\frac{R - e_1}{1 - R \times \frac{e_2}{e_1}} \right] \quad (1)$$

where R is the ratio of absorbances (λA) measured at the wavelengths of maximum absorbance of the acid and basic forms of the mCP indicator dye (434 and 578 nm, respectively), corrected for a reference absorbance value (usually 730 nm) where mCP is not absorbing ($R = (578\lambda A - 730\lambda A)/(434\lambda A - 730\lambda A)$), the term $p(K_2^T e_2)$ combines the second dissociation constant of the indicator dye and the e_2 molar absorptivity ratio of the indicator dye, the other terms e_1 and $\frac{e_3}{e_2}$ are also molar absorptivity ratios. Except for R , the terms in Eq. 1 are obtained from experiments involving potentiometric measurements of buffer solutions with pH_T assigned by an electrochemical cell without liquid junction, known as Harned cell (Buck et al. 2002; Dickson et al. 2016; Capitaine et al. 2023) and are therefore traced to a primary pH_T standard. The terms in Eq. 1 were obtained for specific mCP batches, either unpurified (UNPUR) (Clayton and Byrne 1993) or purified (PUR) (Liu et al. 2011; Loucaides et al. 2017; Müller and Rehder 2018), and parameterized as functions of temperature and salinity over validated ranges (Supporting Information Table S1 and Supporting Information Fig. S1).

The evolution of the spectrophotometric method primarily concerns the transition from unpurified to purified mCP, and the parameterization of the terms in Eq. 1 for the UNPUR and PUR mCP solutions, within different conditions of salinity and temperature. This parameterization depends on the availability of buffer reference materials for pH_T that are characterized using Harned cells (Buck et al. 2002; Capitaine et al. 2023). However, before the first PUR mCP characterization by Liu et al. (2011), a previous work detected impurities in UNPUR mCP solutions absorbing at 434 nm (Yao et al. 2007) that might be corrected using an estimate of the corresponding absorbance contribution of those impurities at 434 nm (${}_{434}A_{\text{imp}}$) when measuring seawater samples for spectrophotometric pH_T, of course, using an UNPUR mCP and assuming there are no impurities absorbing at 578 nm (Douglas and Byrne 2017). The quantification of ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp}}$ and the correction of absorbances obtained with UNPUR mCP to mimic measurements with PUR mCP are still a matter of discussion (Takeshita et al. 2021; Woosley 2021; Fong et al. 2024).

These former issues render the current spectrophotometric pH_T method not fully compliant with metrological fundamentals, such as traceability to the SI, validation with reference materials, and the availability of a properly defined uncertainty budget (Dickson et al. 2016; Carter et al. 2024a). A Joint Research Project in the EURAMET-EMPIR Programme called SapHTies (reference 20NRM06) is making important progress towards establishing a metrologically assessed spectrophotometric pH_T method.

The current situation for seawater spectrophotometric pH_T data challenges is the feasibility, reliability, and usability of the measurements considering three main issues: (i) there is

no commercially available purified mCP; (ii) seawater spectrophotometric pH_T measurements from different or even the same laboratories transitioning from UNPUR to PUR mCP are inconsistent; and (iii) incoherencies between measured and calculated pH_T (Supporting Information Fig. S2) from discrete measurements of either total dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) and total alkalinity (TA) or fugacity of CO₂ (*f*CO₂) and DIC, exceed the climate-goal requirements. These points highlight our partial understanding of the CO₂ chemistry in the ocean and/or a lack of coherence in the measurements. Consequently, the chemical oceanography community faces difficulties in compiling data products for seawater CO₂ system data with informed uncertainties and in establishing calibration procedures for sensor-based pH_T and *f*CO₂ data (Carter et al. 2024a). Clear examples of this declining confidence in the value chain of seawater pH_T data include that (i) spectrophotometric pH_T data will be reported *as is* in the next version of the Global Ocean Data Product (GLODAPv3), a flagship data product for seawater CO₂ system data (Tanhua et al. 2021), with no secondary quality control applied; and (ii) since 2022, GCOS no longer includes pH as a climate indicator.

This work provides a clear procedure to harmonize UNPUR and PUR mCP spectrophotometric pH_T measurements based on replicate real seawater samples across a wide range of oceanographic conditions, with corresponding absorbance values and mCP characterization information provided. This procedure is also implemented in a ship-based time-series in the Northeast Atlantic Ocean, where we additionally tested an empirical approach based on processed UNPUR mCP pH_T data. In all cases, spectrophotometric pH_T data are consistent to within 0.003 pH_T units.

Materials and procedures

UNPUR-PUR data compilation: Cruise data with natural seawater replicate measurements of spectrophotometric pH_T performed with unpurified and purified mCP

During seven cruises spanning from 2018 to 2023, replicate seawater pH_T samples were collected and measured using both UNPUR and PUR mCP. These measurements, together with measurements of TA and dissolved inorganic nutrients, were performed along the GO-SHIP/Med-SHIP line MED01 (Schroeder et al. 2015) repeated in 2018 as MSM72 (Hainbucher et al. 2020), the 2019, 2020, and 2021 RADPROF (Finisterre Deep Section) cruises, and the 2018, 2021, and 2023 RADCAN (Cantabrian Sea Time Series) cruises, the latter two being Spanish hydrographic programs contributing to the IEOOS (Spanish Institute of Oceanography Observing System; Tel et al. 2016) in the Northeast Atlantic and Bay of Biscay, respectively. The resulting dataset covered waters with a wide range of physical and biogeochemical characteristics (Fig. 1; Table 1).

Seawater CO₂ system variables, pH_T and TA, were sampled and measured following Dickson et al. (2007). Samples for pH_T were collected directly from the Niskin bottles into cylindrical optical glass cells with a 10-cm pathlength, filled to overflowing, and immediately stoppered. After sampling, the cells were thermostated to 25°C and measured within approximately 3 h. Temperature was controlled with a JULABO (12 L) thermostatic bath. All absorbance readings were obtained with a non-automated procedure in the thermostated (25°C ± 0.2°C) cell compartment of a SHIMADZU UV-2600 double-beam spectrophotometer (photometric accuracy 0.003, wavelength accuracy 0.3 nm, wavelength repeatability 0.005 nm, stray light < 0.005%) with a 1 nm bandwidth. To verify wavelength and absorbance accuracy, holmium oxide

Fig. 1. Stations with paired seawater pH_T measurements using UNPUR and PUR mCP from this study (Table 1), spanning cruises in the Mediterranean Sea (MSM72) and the Northeast Atlantic Ocean (RADCAN and RADPROF). The RADPROF reference section in the Northeast Atlantic is represented by black circles.

Table 1. Basic information for the cruises included within the UNPUR-PUR compilation, containing paired seawater pH_T measurements using UNPUR and PUR mCP. For each cruise, the alias, expocode (if available), research vessel, and sampling date are provided. The ranges of salinity, total alkalinity (TA), and pH on the total hydrogen ion scale at 25°C and 1 atm, calculated using the CB93 formulation, for UNPUR mCP (pH_UNPUR_CB93) are also provided. The number of samples is indicated in parentheses.

Cruise alias Expocode	Research vessel Date	Salinity	TA (μmol kg ⁻¹)	pH_UNPUR_CB93
MSM72 06M220180302	R/V Maria S. Merian March 2018	36.45–39.29	2397–2632 (149)	7.86–8.00 (157)
RADCAN 2018 NA	R/V Ramón Margalef August 2018	34.90–35.80	2327–2365 (35)	7.73–8.05 (35)
RADPROF 2019 29RM20190818	R/V Ramón Margalef August 2019	34.90–36.15	2317–2396 (38)	7.72–7.99 (38)
RADPROF 2020 29AH20200708	R/V Sarmiento de Gamboa July 2020	34.89–36.08	2315–2386 (43)	7.72–7.96 (45)
RADCAN 2021 NA	R/V Ramón Margalef August 2021	34.97–35.78	2333–2361 (11)	7.74–7.98 (12)
RADPROF 2021 29RM20210814	R/V Ramón Margalef August 2021	34.90–36.17	2316–2389 (44)	7.72–7.99 (47)
RADCAN 2023 NA	R/V Ramón Margalef July 2023	34.90–35.78	—	7.73–7.96 (17)

filters (Hellma GmbH, 667-UV5 Type) were measured at the start of each cruise. After establishing the spectrophotometer baseline using the seawater sample without mCP, absorbance readings were taken at four wavelengths (434, 487.6, 578, and 730 nm) in triplicate cycles per sample. Mean absorbances at each wavelength ($xxx\lambda A$, where xxx refers to each wavelength) were used to calculate the absorbance mean ratio, R ($R = (578\lambda A - 730\lambda A)/(434\lambda A - 730\lambda A)$). The uncertainty in R , based on SHIMADZU specifications, is 0.006. Absorbance readings at the isosbestic point (487.6 nm, denoted as $488\lambda A$) were used to control the amount (and consequently the concentration within the samples) of mCP added (50 μL) with an adjustable repeat pipette (Eppendorf Multipette plus). Solutions of 2 mmol L⁻¹ of UNPUR mCP (Sigma Aldrich 90% purity) were prepared either in aged seawater for the 2018–2020 cruises (batch #11517KC) or in 0.7 M NaCl for the 2021 (batch #11517KC) and 2023 (batch #07005HH) cruises. Similarly, 2 mmol L⁻¹ solutions of PUR mCP (provided by Prof. Byrne, USF, US) were prepared in 0.7 M NaCl (batch FB5-2017 for the 2018–2022 cruises, and a mixture of FB5-2017 and FB6-2021 for the 2023 cruise). Further details are provided in Supporting Information Table S2. Aged seawater from Certified Reference Materials was used in 2018–2020 cruises as being a more stable medium; however, we realized mercury chloride interfered in the ${}_{434}A_{imp}$ quantification.

The addition of the mCP causes a small pH change in the sample (e.g., Li et al. 2020). During each cruise, a double addition correction (ΔR correction) was determined for each mCP over the working pH_T range (see Supporting Information Table S2). The parameterizations used to calculate pH_T from Eq. 1 are those by Clayton and Byrne (1993) (CB93 hereafter)

for UNPUR mCP and Müller and Rehder (2018) (MR18 hereafter) for PUR mCP (Supporting Information Table S1). Calculated pH_T values are identified with subscripts corresponding to the type of mCP (UNPUR or PUR) and formulation used (CB93 or MR18). Any deviations from the 25°C measurement temperature were corrected using the measured pH_T, TA, and dissolved inorganic nutrients in the CO2SYS package for Matlab® (Van Heuven et al. 2011), with option 10 for the CO₂ constants (Lueker et al. 2000) and option 1 for the total boron to chlorinity ratio (Uppström 1974) and sulfate constant (Dickson 1990), as agreed by the GLODAPv2 team (Velo et al. 2010; Olsen et al. 2016). All pH_T data discussed in this work are reported at 25°C and atmospheric pressure. The overall pH_T precision for all cruises is better than 0.002 pH units based on sample replicates, and the assigned total uncertainty is considered to be 0.01 pH units (Dickson et al. 2007; Müller and Rehder 2018; Waters et al. 2016).

Total alkalinity samples were taken after the pH_T samples in 500 mL borosilicate bottles and stored in a dark, dry place to equilibrate to laboratory temperature ($\approx 21^\circ\text{C}$). They were measured on board within a maximum of 1 d after sampling. Total alkalinity was measured using a double end-point potentiometric titration (Perez and Fraga 1987; Pérez et al. 2000; Mintrop et al. 2000). Total alkalinity accuracy was verified with CO₂-in-seawater Reference Materials (RMs; Dickson et al. 2003), and the total uncertainty is 3 μmol kg⁻¹. The TA precision is 2 μmol kg⁻¹ based on sample replicates.

Samples for dissolved inorganic nutrients, silicate and phosphate, were taken into 12 mL sterile polypropylene tubes and immediately frozen and stored until analysis during the RADPROF and RADCAN cruises. After careful defrosting and

shaking of the samples, dissolved inorganic nutrients were determined by Segmented Flow Analysis (Aminot and Krouel 2007) with a SEAL Analytical QuAatro analyzer using colorimetric methods (Becker et al. 2020). Reference Material for Nutrients in Seawater (RMNS, Kanso, Japan) with different concentration ranges, along with low-nutrient seawater, was used for quality control of the analyses. During the MSM72 cruise, dissolved inorganic nutrients were measured on board using a QuAatro analyzer with similar techniques and quality control procedures (Hainbucher et al. 2020). Overall, the uncertainty in dissolved inorganic nutrient concentrations is 0.2% based on RMNS.

The UNPUR-PUR compilation comprises raw absorbance and temperature paired data from UNPUR and PUR mCP, allowing pH_T calculation using any parameterization. As a reference, only pH_T at 25°C calculated using UNPUR *R* values and the CB93 parameterization is provided. Measured TA and ancillary information, such as time and location, physical variables (pressure, temperature, and salinity from calibrated Conductivity, Temperature, and Depth [CTD] sensors), and chemical variables (dissolved inorganic nutrient concentrations for silicate and phosphate), are also provided. The compiled dataset is publicly available in lvarez et al. (2025a).

RADPROF 2018–2023 cruise data: A time-series case study in the Northeast Atlantic Ocean transitioning from unpurified to purified mCP measurements for spectrophotometric pH_T

The observational program IEOOS comprises a series of ship-based stations monitoring hydrographic, biogeochemical, and biological variables at different spatial and temporal scales

along several reference sections transversal to the Spanish coast (Tel et al. 2016). One of these is the RADPROF program, which covered the Galicia-Cantabrian region from 2003 to 2010 with the aim of understanding the mechanisms governing seasonal variability in this region (Prieto et al. 2013). Since 2011, only the Finisterre Deep Hydrographic RADPROF section in the Galician region (Fig. 1) has been carried out annually in summer.

In this work, we use data from six annual RADPROF sections between 2018 and 2023 (Table 2). Detailed descriptions of the sampling, analytical, and quality control procedures can be found in each cruise's metadata and report available through the OCADS (NOAA) and SeaDataNet repositories, where the expocode and the cruise alias (Table 1), respectively, should be used as search references. The sampling, analytical practices, and quality control for pH_T and TA measurements are consistent with those described in the UNPUR-PUR compilation (lvarez et al. 2025a). Values for pH_T (pH on the total hydrogen ion scale at 25°C and 1 atm) are calculated as detailed in previous sections using either UNPUR and/or PUR mCP absorbance data, depending on the mCP used during each cruise. The repeatability or coherence of the physical and chemical variables across the six RADPROF cruises is demonstrated by the agreement of the yearly mean values for potential temperature, salinity, TA, and *R* (ΔR corrected) values within the lower Northeast Atlantic Deep Water (NADW) layer (Supporting Information Table S3), corresponding to waters with $\sigma_4 > 45.84 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ (Lherminier et al. 2007). A z-score analysis confirms that all data fall within one standard deviation of the cruise data for each variable, with the exception of RADPROF 2023, where an emergency on board limited

Table 2. Basic information for the RADPROF 2018 to 2023 cruises included in this work. For each cruise, the alias, expocode, research vessel, and sampling date are listed. The ranges of salinity and TA (number of samples in parentheses) are given. The number (*N*) of pH_T measurements performed using unpurified (UNPUR) and purified (PUR) mCP is also provided. Some cruises include only single mCP measurements, either with UNPUR (2018) or PUR (2022 and 2023) mCP, while the 2019, 2020, and 2021 cruises contain paired pH_T measurements reported in the UNPUR–PUR compilation (Table 1). Additional information about the UNPUR and PUR mCP used during each cruise is available in Supporting Information Table S2.

Cruise alias	Research vessel date	Salinity	TA ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$)	<i>N</i> UNPUR/PUR
RADPROF 2018 29RM20180818	R/V Ramn Margalef August 2018	34.90–36.17	2316–2393 (303)	430/NA
RADPROF 2019 29RM20190818	R/V Ramn Margalef August 2019	34.90–36.18	2315–2396 (228)	401/38
RADPROF 2020 29AH20200708	R/V Sarmiento de Gamboa July 2020	34.89–36.13	2310–2390 (263)	420/45
RADPROF 2021 29RM20210814	R/V Ramn Margalef August 2021	34.90–36.17	2313–2389 (215)	370/47
RADPROF 2022 29RM20220614	R/V Ramn Margalef June 2022	34.90–36.15	2315–2392 (273)	NA/434
RADPROF 2023 29RM20230704	R/V Ramn Margalef July 2023	34.90–36.19	2313–2393 (183)	NA/311

sampling to a few stations deeper than 4000 m. The absorbance values at 434 nm (434λA) and 487.6 nm (488λA) provide insights into the pH_T of the layer and the amount of mCP added to the samples; respectively, both are essential for calculations to correct any mCP impurity.

Experimental laboratory analysis to obtain ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp}}$ for UNPUR and PUR mCP

Commercially available mCP contains impurities that are assumed to only absorb at 434 nm and have negligible absorption at 578 nm (Yao et al. 2007; Liu et al. 2011). To quantify the impact of those impurities on the spectrophotometric pH_T measurements, Douglas and Byrne (2017) proposed a simple correction method for absorbance values obtained with UNPUR mCP. This method is based on an experimentally obtained correction term that characterizes the contribution of mCP impurities to the absorbance measured at 434 nm, denoted as ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp}}$ (Eq. 2, which can be rearranged to Eq. 3):

$${}_{434}A_{\text{imp}} = \left(1 - \frac{e_3}{e_2} \times R\right) \times 434\lambda A \quad (2)$$

$${}_{434}A_{\text{imp}} = 434\lambda A - \frac{e_3}{e_2} \times 578\lambda A \quad (3)$$

In Eqs. 2 and 3, 434λA, 578λA, and R correspond to absorbance values in a 0.71 M ionic strength solution at pH 12 after adding UNPUR mCP, typically over a range of mCP additions and therefore varying 488λA values. The term $\frac{e_3}{e_2}$ is a ratio of molar absorptivities attributed to the basic form of mCP. In Douglas and Byrne (2017), the $\frac{e_3}{e_2}$ parameterization is that by Liu et al. (2011). However, several studies (Takeshita et al. 2021; Woosley 2021; Fong et al. 2024) reported negative ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp}}$ values for UNPUR mCP from different manufacturers when applying the Liu et al. (2011) $\frac{e_3}{e_2}$ parameterization (derived in artificial seawater) in Eq. 2 or 3. Conversely, using the DeGrandpre et al. (2014) $\frac{e_3}{e_2}$ parameterization (derived in NaCl solutions) yielded more realistic ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp}}$ values. These findings, especially Fong et al. (2024), highlight the need for further research on the $\frac{e_3}{e_2}$ parameterization. In addition, the ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp}}$ term reflects impurities absorbing at 434 nm, or possibly at 578 nm (though not evaluated), which are specific to the mCP manufacturer and production batch. As an absorbance, ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp}}$ magnitude should be scaled linearly to the mCP concentration in the seawater samples compared to the pH 12 samples, following the Beer–Lambert law. PUR mCP may still contain impurities that can be quantified using the same procedure or the recently proposed Soft Independent Modeling of Class Analogy (SIMCA) method by Fong et al. (2024).

In Douglas and Byrne (2017), the procedure to obtain ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp}}$ values is briefly outlined in their Table 1: the terms in Eq. 3 are measured using single or repeated absorbance cycles after adding the usual volume of mCP (in their case, 10 μL of

4 mM mCP solution to 10 cm pathlength cells, approximately 3.3 μM mCP in the cells) to pH 12 samples of a NaOH solution in 0.71 M NaCl background, thermostated at 25°C. Note that at pH 12, 434λA values (ranging from 0.03 to 0.10) are much smaller than 578λA values (ranging from 0.4 to 1.6). Therefore, the uncertainty in ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp}}$ depends on the repeatability of measurements (including operator, sample preparation, pipette precision, and temperature control) and the spectrophotometer's accuracy, precision, and linearity in absorbance measurements. Thus, it is crucial to verify wavelength and absorbance accuracy before conducting any ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp}}$ quantification.

In this study, we modify the Douglas and Byrne (2017) method to calculate ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp}}$ over a range of 488λA values, using the $\frac{e_3}{e_2}$ parameterization from DeGrandpre et al. (2014). This $\frac{e_3}{e_2}$ parameterization depends only on temperature and yields the lowest values compared to other available parameterizations (see Supporting Information Fig. S). We are aware that results from the SapHTies project will soon provide a new parameterization for Eq. 1, including $\frac{e_3}{e_2}$ as a function of temperature and salinity, as well (Martínez-Cabanas, personal communication).

Details on our method to obtain the ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp}}$ are provided in Supporting Information Text 1. Briefly, absorbance measurements at 434, 487.6, 578, and 730 nm are performed on at least five replicate samples (0.71 M NaCl solution of pH 12) in 10 cm pathlength cells thermostated at 25°C. These absorbances are measured in three different mCP concentrations covering both above and below the typical mCP concentration used in the seawater sample analysis (in our case, approximately 3.3 μM mCP in the cells; i.e., 50 μL of 2 mM mCP solution added to 10 cm pathlength cells). For each of the three different mCP volume additions across the five replicates, we calculate mean absorbance values and standard deviations from each repeated cycle. This allows us to derive, for each batch of UNPUR or PUR mCP, a regression line relating ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp}}$ to 488λA. The experimental correction term at the isobestic point, when adding the mCP concentration used for seawater samples to pH 12 samples, is denoted as ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp_exp}}$ at 488λA_{exp}. Assuming absorbance linearity, the impurities correction term for any other isobestic absorbance value in seawater samples is given by Eq. 4:

$${}_{434}A_{\text{imp}} = {}_{434}A_{\text{imp_exp}} \times \frac{488\lambda A}{488\lambda A_{\text{exp}}} \quad (4)$$

Equation 4 accounts for small deviations in mCP concentration between the seawater samples and the pH 12 samples, assuming nominally the same concentration of mCP is added. These deviations may arise from pipetting or operator variability, slight differences in mCP stock concentration, or differences in optical pathlengths between the seawater and pH 12 samples. The experimentally determined ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp_exp}}$ values for the various mCP solutions used in this study are given in

the Supporting Information Table S2. Note that ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp_exp}}$ values are only positive when the DeGrandpre et al. (2014) $\frac{\epsilon_3}{\epsilon_2}$ parameterization is used, that as commented before yields the lowest $\frac{\epsilon_3}{\epsilon_2}$ value.

Harmonizing unpurified and purified spectrophotometric pH_T based on absorbance data and ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp}}$ corrections

We follow the procedure proposed by Douglas and Byrne (2017). Using absorbance measurements (434λA, 488λA, 578λA, all base-line corrected by subtracting 730λA) together with the sample salinity and the temperature from the pH_T measurement (t, usually 25°C), the impurity-corrected absorbance ratio (R_{IC}) is calculated as:

$$R_{IC} = R \times \left\{ 1 + \left[\frac{{}_{434}A_{\text{imp_exp}} \times \frac{488\lambda A}{488\lambda A_{\text{exp}}}}{434\lambda A - {}_{434}A_{\text{imp_exp}} \times \frac{488\lambda A}{488\lambda A_{\text{exp}}}} \right] \right\} \quad (5)$$

where R is the measured absorbance ratio (corrected for ΔR , see Supporting Information Table S2). This equation corrects the effect of impurities absorbing at 434 nm in spectrophotometric pH_T measurements using any UNPUR or partially PUR mCP that has a meaningful ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp_exp}}$ value. The ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp_exp}}$ term scales linearly with the concentration of mCP added to seawater samples relative to the concentration in the pH 12 experiment, as described in the previous section. Although this correction was not explicitly formulated in Eq. 13 of Douglas and Byrne (2017), it was discussed in their work and further emphasized in Fong et al. (2024).

The experimentally obtained values of ${}_{434}A_{\text{imp_exp}}$ for the different mCP solutions, both UNPUR and PUR mCP, used in this study are provided in Supporting Information Table S2. In that table, the mean 488λA value for all samples in each cruise is similar to the corresponding 488λA_{exp} for the PUR and/or UNPUR mCP used in the pH 12 experiments. For each individual sample and cruise, Eq. 5 is applied using the measured 488λA value specific to every sample and cruise.

The former impurity-corrected absorbance ratios (R_{IC}) are then used as input in pH_T parameterizations developed for PUR mCP, such as those by Liu et al. (2011), Loucaides et al. (2017), or Müller and Rehder (2018) (see Supporting Information Table S1). In this study, we used the MR18 parameterization because it approximately covers the salinity range of the studied samples (Table 1). Temperature deviations from the reference 25°C measurement are corrected by introducing the measured pH_T, TA, and dissolved inorganic nutrients data into the CO2SYS package for Matlab® as detailed in the UNPUR-PUR compilation section.

As mentioned previously, all pH_T values are identified with subscripts indicating the type of mCP used (UNPUR or PUR), the parameterization applied (CB93 or MR18), and the absorbance ratio type (either original (R_{orig}) or impurity-corrected (R_{IC}) with Eq. 5), with all R corrected for ΔR (see Supporting

Information Table S2). In this work, we use four different pH_T calculations:

- pH_UNPUR_CB93: pH on the total hydrogen ion scale at 25°C and 1 atm measured with UNPUR mCP, using R_{orig} in the CB93 parameterization.
- pH_UNPUR_MR18: pH on the total hydrogen ion scale at 25°C and 1 atm measured with UNPUR mCP, using R_{orig} in the MR18 parameterization.
- pH_UNPUR_IC_MR18: pH on the total hydrogen ion scale at 25°C and 1 atm measured with UNPUR mCP, using R_{IC} in the MR18 parameterization.
- pH_PUR_IC_MR18: pH on the total hydrogen ion scale at 25°C and 1 atm measured with PUR mCP, using R_{IC} in the MR18 parameterization.

This methodology was applied to the UNPUR-PUR data compilation, which contains paired pH_T measurements with both UNPUR and PUR mCP, as well as the RADPROF 2018–2023 cruises during which pH_T measurements transitioned from UNPUR to PUR mCP (see Tables 1 and 2; Supporting Information Table S2).

Harmonizing unpurified and purified spectrophotometric pH_T based on empirical approaches from pH_UNPUR_CB93

We examine the potential for referring pH_UNPUR_CB93 data to pH_T values corrected for mCP impurities and calculated using the MR18 parameterization. This is achieved by deriving empirical regression models based on either pH_PUR_IC_MR18 or pH_UNPUR_IC_MR18 values. A comparable empirical approach was proposed in Yao et al. (2007) to reconcile pH_T measurements made with mCP from Kodak to those using mCP from Sigma-Aldrich, calculating pH_T values for both sets of absorbance data using the CB93 parameterization. Notably, the CB93 parameterization was developed using Kodak mCP, which Yao et al. (2007) identified as having a high content of impurities absorbing at 434 nm. In contrast, other vendors such as TCI-GR and Sigma-Aldrich were reported to produce mCP with lower impurity levels. Using TRIS buffer solutions, Yao et al. (2007) showed that pH_UNPUR_CB93 measurements with Sigma-Aldrich mCP were generally higher than those with Kodak mCP, particularly at higher seawater pH_T values (i.e., pH_UNPUR_CB93_Sigma-Aldrich > pH_UNPUR_CB93_Kodak). To account for this difference, they proposed a quadratic empirical correction for Kodak-based pH_T measurements. Similarly, Liu et al. (2011), using buffered solutions, observed empirical differences between pH_UNPUR and pH_PUR, both calculated with their own formulation across various commercial UNPUR mCP and their in-house PUR mCP. Although they did not calculate explicit correction models, their results consistently showed that pH_PUR > pH_UNPUR (both calculated with Liu et al. 2011), indicating that UNPUR-based measurements tend

to underestimate pH_T in the higher seawater pH_T range (> 7.95).

Liu et al. (2011) formulated, but did not calculate, an empirical correction approach originally suggested by Yao et al. (2007). This method enables the estimation of pH_{PUR} from pH_{UNPUR} when paired measurements using UNPUR mCP (same mCP used with the data to be corrected) and PUR mCP are available over the working range of pH_T, but without associated absorbance data. In this work, we implement and extend this approach using real seawater samples, leading to the following equations:

$$\text{pH}_{\text{PUR_proxy}} = \text{pH}_{\text{UNPUR_CB93}} + \Delta\text{pH} \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta\text{pH} = f(\text{pH}_{\text{UNPUR_CB93}}^2, \text{pH}_{\text{UNPUR_CB93}}, t_{\text{is}}, S_{\text{is}}, \text{Pres}_{\text{is}}) \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta\text{pH1} = \text{pH}_{\text{PUR_IC_MR18}} - \text{pH}_{\text{UNPUR_CB93}} \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta\text{pH2} = \text{pH}_{\text{UNPUR_IC_MR18}} - \text{pH}_{\text{UNPUR_CB93}} \quad (9)$$

The correction term ΔpH is modeled as a quadratic function of the original pH_T measurements with UNPUR mCP (pH_{UNPUR_CB93}) and key hydrography variables (in situ (is) temperature (t), salinity (S) and pressure (Pres)).

As commented previously, based on the MR18 parameterization, we use either pH_{PUR_IC_MR18} (samples measured with PUR mCP, ΔpH1 , Eq. 8) or pH_{UNPUR_IC_MR18} (samples measured with UNPUR mCP corrected for impurities, i.e., reconciled to purified values, ΔpH2 , Eq. 9). The empirical models and their regression coefficients for the two regression models are provided in Supporting Information Table S4, while the corresponding pH_T residuals are visualized in Supporting Information Fig. S4. This empirical correction strategy will be implemented and discussed based on the RADPROF 2018–2023 cruise data where we transitioned from UNPUR to PUR mCP to measure pH_T.

Results and discussion

UNPUR-PUR compilation: Comparison of unpurified and purified spectrophotometric pH_T on duplicate samples

Up to our knowledge, this is the first time that paired pH_T measurements using both UNPUR and PUR mCP have been presented for real seawater samples. Previous studies, such as Yao et al. (2007), Liu et al. (2011), and Douglas and Byrne (2017), focused on comparisons using buffer solutions, as discussed earlier. More recent works examining pH_T time series have acknowledged discrepancies between pH_T values obtained with UNPUR and PUR mCP. However, they have not quantitatively assessed the temporal coherency of these datasets (Frangoulis et al. 2024; Muller-Karger et al. 2019). Other recent studies have applied the impurity correction method proposed by Douglas and Byrne (2017), either by implementing the $_{434}A_{\text{imp}}$ correction (Trucco-Pignata

et al. 2019; Miller and Kelley 2021; Takeshita et al. 2021; Liu et al. 2022; Singh et al. 2023) or by applying a fixed pH offset to the final values (Lyu et al. 2019).

A time-series transitioning from UNPUR to PUR mCP pH_T measurements will exhibit a pattern similar to the black dots in Fig. 2. Notably, the largest discrepancies occur in the lower end of the seawater pH range, where pH_{UNPUR_CB93} values are higher than pH_{PUR_IC_MR18}. This observation contrasts with previous findings by Yao et al. (2007), Liu et al. (2011), and Douglas and Byrne (2017), who reported that pH_{UNPUR_CB93} underestimates pH_T values in the higher seawater pH_T range. This conclusion arises from inadequate pairing of R values and parameterizations. For instance, the blue dots in Fig. 2 reflect this issue: R values derived from UNPUR mCP are input into a parameterization developed for PUR mCP (e.g., MR18 in our case, but similar results would be obtained if using Liu et al. (2011) or Loucaides et al. (2017); see Supporting Information Fig. S1F S1). Note that the distribution of the blue dots resembles the results from Yao et al. (2007), Liu et al. (2011), and Douglas and Byrne (2017).

The observed differences between pH_{UNPUR_CB93} and pH_{PUR_MR18} (particularly the fact that pH_{UNPUR_CB93} > pH_{PUR_MR18} at low seawater pH_T) arise from the interplay of three key factors: (1) absorbance values measured using UNPUR mCP differ from those obtained with PUR mCP, primarily due to impurities that absorb at 434 nm, with a negligible contribution at 578 nm. Since R is a ratio (578 nm/434 nm), this means that R_{PUR} tends to be higher than R_{UNPUR} , as 434 nm_{PUR} is always lower than 434 nm_{UNPUR}. The impact of impurities becomes more significant at higher seawater pH_T, where 434 nm values are lower and thus more sensitive to small 434 nm changes due to impurities. Our results confirm this behavior (see Supporting Information Fig. S3A,C), consistent with those reported by Yao et al. (2007), who found that pH_{UNPUR_CB93} (Sigma-Aldrich mCP) > pH_{UNPUR_CB93} (Kodak mCP), with Sigma-Aldrich being a proxy for PUR mCP. In our data, we reproduce their results only when R values from PUR mCP are input into the CB93 parameterization, i.e., pH_{PUR_CB93} > pH_{UNPUR_CB93} (results not shown). (2) The second fact relates to the CB93 parameterization, which was developed using UNPUR Kodak mCP, while both MR18 and Liu et al. (2011) parameterizations were developed using PUR mCP. Consequently, any term in Eq. 1 ($p(K_2^T e_2)$, $\frac{e_3}{e_2}$ and e_1) differs between parameterizations for UNPUR and PUR mCP (see Supporting Information Fig. S2A,B,C). Even if R values would be equal, pH_T calculated with CB93 would be higher than pH_T calculated with Liu et al. (2011) by more than 0.01 pH units due to the difference in the terms in Eq. 1 (Supporting Information Fig. S2F). However, this scenario is theoretical, in practice R_{UNPUR} is always lower than R_{PUR} , especially at high seawater pH_T. Thus, when comparing pH_{UNPUR_CB93} with pH_{PUR_MR18} at high seawater pH_T values, the higher pH_T output of the CB93 parameterization

Fig. 2. Differences in pH_T for paired measurements using unpurified (UNPUR) and purified (PUR) mCP from the cruises shown in Fig. 1 and listed in Table 1, plotted against pH_T measured with PUR mCP and calculated using the Müller and Rehder (2018) (MR18) parameterization. Black dots represent pH_T differences between values calculated from UNPUR mCP absorbance ratios (R) input into the Clayton and Byrne (1993) (CB93) parameterization, and those from R_{PUR_IC} input into the MR18 parameterization. Blue dots show pH_T differences calculated using MR18 for both R_{UNPUR} and R_{PUR_IC} . Orange dots show pH_T differences between R_{UNPUR_IC} and R_{PUR_IC} , both calculated using MR18 parameterization. R_{UNPUR_IC} or R_{PUR_IC} denote R values corrected for impurities using Eq. 5, based on $_{434}A_{imp_exp}$ values and $_{488}A_{exp}$ from Supporting Information Table S2, and calculated with the $\frac{\epsilon_3}{\epsilon_2}$ ratio from DeGrandpre et al. (2014). Cyan dots show pH_T differences between R_{UNPUR_IC} and R_{PUR_IC} , both calculated using MR18 parameterization. R_{UNPUR_IC} denote R values corrected for impurities using Eq. 5, based on $_{434}A_{imp_exp}$ values and $_{488}A_{exp}$ from Supporting Information Table S2, and calculated with the $\frac{\epsilon_3}{\epsilon_2}$ ratio from Liu et al. (2011) and no correction applied to R_{PUR_IC} . All R values are corrected for ΔR (double-addition correction). The figure legend includes the mean and standard deviation of each set of pH_T differences. The gray and yellow shaded regions correspond to 0.003 and 0.02 pH units intervals, respectively. All pH values are reported on the total hydrogen ion scale at 25°C and 1 atm.

appears to compensate for the lower R_{UNPUR} values. This results in a better match between pH_{UNPUR_CB93} and pH_{PUR_MR18} , with differences within 0.003 pH units (see black dots in Fig. 2). (3) The third factor concerns using TRIS buffers as reference to develop each UNPUR or PUR mCP pH_T parameterization. CB93 relied on TRIS pH_T values assigned by Dickson (1993) and based on measurements of Ramette et al. (1977). In contrast, Liu et al. (2011) used values from DeValls and Dickson (1998), and MR18 employed their own TRIS pH_T values, which are in agreement with DeValls and Dickson (1998) at salinities above 20. Therefore, it is not surprising that at high seawater pH_T values (where TRIS pHT is ≈ 8.1 at 25°C and 35 salinity), different parameterizations, even for different mCP purities, tend to converge. However, DeValls and Dickson (1998) recommended adding 0.0047 pH_T units to pH_T values calculated using CB93 parameterization to account for discrepancies between Dickson (1993) and Ramette et al. (1977) and their revised TRIS characterization values. This

correction has been applied inconsistently by the community: ad hoc applied to UNPUR pH_T measurements depending on the research group. Some studies have used it to improve internal consistency between measured and calculated seawater CO_2 system variables (e.g., Lee et al. 2000), while others do not confirm this benefit (Álvarez et al. 2020; García-Ibáñez et al. 2022). In this study, no 0.0047 pH_T units correction was applied to any of the pH_T data used.

Assuming no impurities absorbing at 578 nm, any potential impurities absorbing at 434 nm present in both UNPUR and PUR mCP used in our UNPUR-PUR compilation were experimentally evaluated to determine their corresponding $_{434}A_{imp_exp}$ values (see Supporting Information Table S2). These values were input into Eq. 5 and used with the MR18 parameterization to compute the impurity-corrected R (R_{IC}) and pH_T values. Notably, the corrected-to-purified pH_T values obtained using a commercially available UNPUR mCP (Sigma-Aldrich, 90% purity) agreed within 0.003 pH units with pH_T

values obtained with a PUR mCP (provided by Prof. Byrne's laboratory) (see orange dots in Fig. 2). This agreement held across our working pH_T range of ~7.7–8.0 and spanned a wide range of depth and salinity conditions (see Supporting Information Fig. S1B,D,F).

By refining the original Douglas and Byrne (2017) correction methodology ($_{434}A_{imp}$), our results validate and enhance this impurity-correction approach, ensuring internal consistency in both experimental and time-series analyses where pH_T measurements transition from UNPUR to partially or fully PUR mCP. This holds true provided that absorbance values are available.

Importantly, our findings caution against the use of R with inappropriate parameterizations, as this can lead to misleading and erroneous pH_T results (e.g., blue dots in Fig. 2). Furthermore, $_{434}A_{imp_exp}$ values should be evaluated for both UNPUR and PUR mCPs using the same $\frac{e_3}{e_2}$ parameterization to ensure coherent values for $_{434}A_{imp_exp}$. For example, evaluating only UNPUR mCP and applying the Liu et al. (2011) $\frac{e_3}{e_2}$ parameterization in Eq. 5, without correcting PUR mCP, produces an inconsistent and incoherent time-series (see cyan dots in Fig. 2).

We therefore strongly recommend retaining all raw absorbance data and associated data and metadata, including temperature and mCP batch information. This ensures traceability and facilitates updates in case new parameterizations appear. Given access to the original absorbances, any new or improved pH_T parameterization can be implemented retroactively and consistently.

RADPROF 2018–2023 cruise data: Harmonizing unpurified and purified spectrophotometric pH_T based on absorbance data and $_{434}A_{imp}$ corrections

The RADPROF time-series for pH_T in the Northeast Atlantic illustrates the case of the transition from pH_T measurements using UNPUR (2018 to 2021) to PUR mCP (2022 and 2023), as detailed in Supporting Information Table S2. We leverage the low temporal variability of the bottom layer in this region, which is occupied by lower North Atlantic Deep Water (NADW) influenced by Antarctic Bottom Water (McCartney 1992; Van Aken 2000), to assess the consistency of the pH_T measurements. This layer is commonly used as a reference for crossover analyses in the GLODAP data synthesis product (Olsen et al. 2016), where, for example, the anthropogenic carbon trend from the 1990s to 2000s is negligible (Pérez et al. 2010).

As presented and discussed in the previous section on the UNPUR-PUR data compilation, we observed a good agreement, within approximately 0.003 pH_T units, between paired measurements of pH_{UNPUR_IC_MR18} and pH_{PUR_IC_MR18}. Here, we focus on the RADPROF cruises from 2018 to 2023. For pH_{PUR_IC_MR18}, no data were available in 2018, only limited data from 2019 to 2021, and full datasets from the

2022 and 2023 cruises (Table 2). To address this, we used absorbance data from UNPUR mCP measurements during 2018–2021 cruises and the $_{434}A_{imp_exp}$ results for each Sigma-Aldrich mCP batch used (Supporting Information Table S2). We applied Eq. 5 to correct R_{UNPUR} into R_{UNPUR_IC} values, which are input into the MR18 parameterization. The lower NADW layer, generally corresponding to waters below 3500 dbar in the Northeast Atlantic, serves as the comparison depth. In this layer, both directly measured and corrected to PUR mCP pH_T values (pH_{PUR_IC_MR18} and pH_{UNPUR_IC_MR18}, respectively) are directly compared (Fig. 3A), showing a mean and standard deviation difference of 0.0019 ± 0.0019 pH units (pH_{UNPUR_IC_MR18} – pH_{PUR_IC_MR18}), which is statistically smaller than 0.003 pH units (according to a Wilcoxon test at the 0.05 significance level). In contrast, the difference between UNPUR and PUR mCP pH_T values is larger, with a mean and standard deviation difference of 0.0073 ± 0.0019 (pH_{UNPUR_CB93} – pH_{PUR_IC_MR18}), which is statistically higher than 0.003 pH units (according to a Wilcoxon test at the 0.05 significance level).

Although the difference between pH_{UNPUR_CB93} and pH_{PUR_IC_MR18} appears nearly constant in deep waters, where vertical pH_T variability is low (Fig. 3A), in upper layers, where vertical pH gradients are more pronounced (Fig. 3B), the pH_{UNPUR_CB93} – pH_{PUR_IC_MR18} values vary as a function of pH_T. Notably, minimum differences occur near the pH_T maximum associated with Mediterranean Water around 1000 dbar (Fig. 3B inset). The yearly mean profiles of the directly comparable pH_{UNPUR_IC_MR18} (solid lines) and pH_{PUR_IC_MR18} (dotted lines) within the upper 2000 dbar (Fig. 3B) reveal a likely ocean acidification signal, particularly within the upper 1000 dbar. This signal would be blurred if comparing pH_{UNPUR_CB93} and pH_{PUR_IC_MR18}.

RADPROF 2018–2023 cruise data: Empirical harmonization of unpurified and purified spectrophotometric pH_T based on pH_{UNPUR_CB93}

We have demonstrated that, by using absorbance data along with the characterization of UNPUR and PUR mCP batches from the 2018 to 2023 RADPROF cruises, it is possible to reconstruct a consistent ship-based pH_T time series, following a revised and improved approach based on Douglas and Byrne (2017). In cases where few or no absorbance data are available, a consistent pH_T time series can still be reconstructed using the empirical quadratic relationships in Supporting Information Table S4 (pH_{PUR_proxy}). These relationships have been shown to accurately reproduce the pH_{UNPUR_IC_MR18} estimates without introducing bias in the distribution of the residuals (Supporting Information Fig. S4). This level of accuracy is not achieved when using linear relationships (Supporting Information Fig. S5; Supporting Information Table S6).

Within the lower NADW layer, the combination of pH_{PUR_proxy} and directly measured pH_{PUR_IC_MR18}

Fig. 3. Legend on next page.

values across all cruises agrees within one standard deviation (7.7333 ± 0.0019 ; see Supporting Information Table S5). The only exception is the 2023 data, which shows slightly lower values, likely due to limited vertical coverage within the lower NADW layer (Fig. 4A). Similarly, the average and standard deviation of pH_UNPUR_CB93 from 2018 to 2021 in this layer (7.7394 ± 0.0018) are significantly higher (according to a one-tailed *t*-test for paired samples, yielding a *p*-value < 0.001 at a 0.05 significance level) than the overall mean of pH_PUR_proxy and pH_PUR_IC_MR18 (7.7333 ± 0.0019).

The envelope of 2018–2021 pH_UNPUR_CB93 values (mean \pm standard deviation) in the upper 2000 dbar (Fig. 4B) nearly encompasses the annual mean profiles of both pH_PUR_proxy and pH_PUR_IC_MR18. These annual mean profiles exhibit a decrease in pH_T over time, indicative of ongoing ocean acidification, particularly pronounced between 2018 and 2019 in the upper 1000 dbar.

Concerns about measurement and data archiving for seawater spectrophotometric pH_T

Seawater pH_T data based on spectrophotometric measurements is typically reported to national and/or international ocean data centers at a standard temperature, most commonly 25°C. This involves applying Eq. 1 using a specific parameterization (see Supporting Information Table S1) to absorbance data, which are rarely reported to the data bases. Ideally, spectrophotometric pH_T metadata should provide details on the pH scale, measurement temperature, mCP, and formulation used, as well as quality assurance and control results (often based on TRIS buffer measurements and repeatability from replicate samples). However, providing such metadata is largely voluntary.

A key and widely used repository for discrete water column seawater CO₂ system data is the Ocean Carbon and Acidification Data System (OCADS) repository (Jiang et al. 2023), which offers a relatively simple metadata template for pH (Jiang et al. 2015). This same template is used for reporting under the UNESCO SDG Indicator 14.3.1, through the International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange Programme (IODE) data portal. Nonetheless, certain metadata elements should be mandatory, such as information on the equipment used, the mCP (including brand and batch,

concentration of the mCP solution, and volume added to the samples), laboratory measurement conditions, parameterization applied, and any corrections made to *R* (e.g., $\Delta R_{434A_{imp}}$) or to pH_T values (e.g., the 0.0047 correction from DelValls and Dickson 1998). In this regard, the metadata reporting template for spectrophotometric pH_T within the pilot initiative Synthesis Product of Ocean Time Series (SPOTS: Lange et al. 2024), which compiles ship-based time-series, stands out as one of the most comprehensive to date.

To our knowledge, no existing ocean data center or data product currently stores the raw absorbance data underlying spectrophotometric pH_T measurements. One of the most widely used seawater CO₂ data products, GLODAP (Lauvset et al. 2016; Olsen et al. 2016), compiles ship-based measurements of inorganic carbon and relevant variables into a standardized, accessible format. GLODAP applies rigorous primary and secondary quality control procedures to ensure internal consistency across a vast number of cruises conducted by different countries and observational programs, despite slight methodological differences among them. GLODAP provides an invaluable service to the observational, modeling, and stakeholder ocean communities by enabling consistent long-term assessments of changes in ocean physics and chemistry due to human activities (Tanhua et al. 2021).

The first version of GLODAP did not include pH data (Key et al. 2004). Later, GLODAPv2 (Olsen et al. 2016) incorporated both potentiometric and spectrophotometric pH measurements, building upon the earlier CARBON IN the Atlantic Ocean (CARINA) effort (Velo et al. 2010). Briefly, the harmonization method combines results from crossover analyses with, when possible, evaluations of consistency between measured pH and pH calculated from DIC and TA, using deep water values as references.

As the availability of spectrophotometric pH_T data increased through successive GLODAPv2 updates in 2021 and 2022, clear evidence emerged regarding the unreliability of some secondary quality control (2QC) corrections applied to spectrophotometric pH_T measurements. Specifically, the latest GLODAPv2.2023 update (Lauvset et al. 2024) chose to omit any 2QC pH_T correction based on internal consistency with pH_T calculated from DIC and TA. This decision was supported by findings that pH_T biases can be pH-dependent, potentially

Fig. 3. Vertical distribution of RADPROF pH values on the total hydrogen ion scale at 25°C and 1 atm (pH_{25T}). **(A)** Deep-water pH_{25T} values (from 2500 dbar to the bottom). Filled circles represent pH_{25T} measured with UNPUR mCP calculated using the CB93 parameterization (pH_UNPUR_CB93) for the 2018–2021 cruises. Open squares correspond to pH_{25T} measured with UNPUR mCP corrected to PUR and calculated with the MR18 parameterization (pH_UNPUR_IC_MR18), also for the 2018–2021 cruises. Filled diamonds represent pH_{25T} measured with PUR mCP calculated using the MR18 parameterization (pH_PUR_IC_MR18) for the 2019–2023 cruises. Solid lines show the mean profiles of the data below 3500 dbar. Notes within the plot provide the mean and standard deviation of pH_{25T} profile differences for waters below 3500 dbar with $\sigma_4 > 45.84 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. **(B)** Yearly mean pH_{25T} profiles in the upper water column (250–1600 dbar) for pH_UNPUR_CB93 (dashed lines), pH_PUR_IC_MR18 (dotted lines), and pH_UNPUR_IC_MR18 (solid lines). The inset shows the mean profile difference between pH_UNPUR_CB93 and pH_UNPUR_IC_MR18 for the 2018–2021 cruises. Both R_{PUR_IC} and R_{UNPUR_IC} values have been corrected for their respective $\Delta R_{434A_{imp_exp}}$ (calculated using the $\frac{e_3}{e_2}$ ratio from DeGrandpre et al. 2014) using Eq. 5, $488\lambda A_{exp}$ for each cruise, as detailed in Supporting Information Table S2, and $488\lambda A$ for each sample. The colorbar in (B) applies to both subplots and indicates the RADPROF cruise year.

Fig. 4. Legend on next page.

leading to erroneous corrections, particularly in low-pH_T seawater (Fong and Dickson 2019; Álvarez et al. 2020; Takeshita et al. 2021; García-Ibáñez et al. 2022; Carter et al. 2024b).

Furthermore, crossover comparisons involving pH_T measured with UNPUR mCP can be misleading due to variations in impurity levels across commercial batches from different manufacturers (Liu et al. 2011; Takeshita et al. 2020; Woosley 2021; Carter et al. 2024a; Fong et al. 2024). Even when using PUR mCP, pH_T measurements can differ by approximately 0.01 pH units between laboratories, as observed in comparisons between U.S. and Japan cruises in the North Pacific (Álvarez et al. 2020).

Given the ongoing development of the spectrophotometric pH_T method (Carter et al. 2024a), which still lacks full metrological traceability to the SI (Dickson et al. 2016; Capitaine et al. 2023), we strongly recommend systematic recovery and archiving of spectrophotometric absorbance data for pH_T, accompanied by comprehensive metadata. Absorbance data can be coherently reprocessed and harmonized, at a minimum, to a common parameterization in which $_{434}A_{imp}$ corrections can be inferred and applied to data obtained using UNPUR mCP. This intermediate step would provide a practical solution while awaiting the development and validation of a fully SI-traceable spectrophotometric pH_T method and corresponding reference materials, as envisioned by international standardization bodies. Such advancements are being facilitated by recent European projects, including SapHTies (EU EMPIR EURAMET project: Metrology for standardized seawater pH_T measurements in support of international and European climate strategies), which will soon provide a new parameterization for purified mCP (Martínez-Cabanas, personal communication) and MINKE (EU INFRAIA project: Metrology for Integrated Marine Management and Knowledge-Transfer Network).

Conclusions

To our knowledge, this is the first time that paired replicate seawater samples for spectrophotometric pH_T measurements using commercially available unpurified (UNPUR) meta-cresol purple (mCP) have been directly compared and harmonized with measurements performed using purified (PUR) mCP (from Prof. Byrne's laboratory, USF, US). Through the UNPUR-

PUR data compilation (replicate measurements spanning a wide range of oceanographic conditions), we have demonstrated that both approaches can be aligned within 0.003 pH units. This level of agreement is achieved when absorbance data obtained with both UNPUR and PUR mCP are carefully evaluated and corrected for impurities, and when the resulting corrected absorbance ratios (R) are input into the same formulation developed for PUR mCP.

Our findings question prior assertions that spectrophotometric pH_T measurements using UNPUR mCP systematically underestimate pH_T in the high seawater pH_T range. These earlier conclusions likely stemmed from the inappropriate use of UNPUR mCP *absorbance ratios* with parameterizations specifically developed for PUR mCP. In contrast, our results show improved agreement between UNPUR and PUR pH_T in the high-pH_T seawater range, and a tendency for UNPUR mCP to overestimate pH_T in the lower seawater pH_T range.

Spectrophotometric pH_T time-series transitioning from UNPUR to PUR mCP measurements can be harmonized to within 0.003 pH units. Using the ship-based RADPROF pH_T time-series from the Northeast Atlantic Ocean (RADPROF 2018–2023 data compilation), and referencing the stable deep layer of North Atlantic Deep Water below 4500 m, we demonstrate the coherence between previous pH_T data derived from UNPUR mCP (impurity-corrected) and recent measurements obtained with PUR mCP. All pH_T values are harmonized to a common parameterization developed for PUR mCP (i.e., Müller and Rehder 2018), where impurity-corrected R s are used. This method relies on recovering the absorbance data measured with UNPUR mCP and estimating the $_{434}A_{imp}$ specific to the UNPUR mCP batch used, and assumes no impurities absorbing at 578 nm. Alternatively, an empirical approach may be applied, using quadratic relationships between original pH_UNPUR_CB93 values and environmental variables (in situ salinity, pressure, and temperature) to correct the data. However, this method requires paired data of pH_UNPUR_CB93 and either impurity-corrected UNPUR mCP pH_T or PUR mCP pH_T, and it carries higher uncertainty regarding the final consistency of the time-series.

Spectrophotometric pH_T measurements are straightforward and widely accessible, offering invaluable insight into the chemical state of seawater and the impacts of anthropogenic pressures on both open-ocean and coastal environments.

Fig. 4. Mean vertical profiles of measured and proxy-to-purified pH values on the total hydrogen ion scale at 25°C and 1 atm (pH_{25T}) for the yearly RADPROF cruises listed in Table 2. **(A)** Deep-water profiles (2500 dbar to the bottom). **(B)** Upper water column (250–1600 dbar). Colored lines for the 2022 and 2023 cruises represent pH_{25T} values measured with PUR mCP calculated using the MR18 parameterization (pH_PUR_IC_MR18). The corresponding R_{PUR_IC} were corrected for their ΔR and $_{434}A_{imp}$ values obtained with the $\frac{e_3}{e_2}$ from DeGrandpre et al. (2014) in Eq. 5; see Supporting Information Table S2. Colored lines for the 2018 to 2021 cruises represent proxy-to-purified pH_{25T} values derived from an empirical approach, where PUR pH_{25T} is estimated from pH_UNPUR_CB93, i.e., pH_T measured with UNPUR mCP and calculated with the CB93 parameterization, which are input into Eqs. 6 and 7, using the ΔpH_2 coefficients provided in Supporting Information Table S4. This empirical correction is based on pH_UNPUR_IC_MR18, i.e., R from UNPUR mCP input into MR18 parameterization and corrected to PUR using Eq. 5 and $_{434}A_{imp}$ values obtained with the $\frac{e_3}{e_2}$ DeGrandpre et al. (2014); see Supporting Information Table S2. The gray shaded areas represent one standard deviation envelope around the mean pH_UNPUR_CB93 profiles for the 2018–2021 cruises.

However, the evolution of the spectrophotometric pH method since the 1990s has proceeded without proper traceability to the SI, which can hinder the accurate interpretation of pH data, particularly for long-term time-series, unless robust harmonization efforts are undertaken. In this context, pH data may unintentionally be perceived as inherently unreliable, as illustrated by the fact that GLODAPv3 will provide pH_T data “as is.” The CO_2 oceanography community strongly anticipates the development and formal adoption of a fully metrologically traceable to SI spectrophotometric pH_T method, corresponding reference materials, and an uncertainty budget approved by international standardization bodies. In the meanwhile, we strongly recommend systematic recovery and archiving of spectrophotometric absorbance data for pH_T , accompanied by comprehensive metadata.

Author Contributions

All authors contributed to data collection, data analysis, writing-review, and editing of the manuscript. Marta Álvarez conceptualized the study and acquired funding. Marta Álvarez wrote (lead), reviewed, and edited the manuscript with contributions from all co-authors.

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Conflicts of Interest

None declared.

Data Availability Statement

The UNPUR-PUR data compilation is freely available in the DIGITAL.CSIC repository in Álvarez et al. (2025a). The example EXCEL file to calculate ${}_{434}\text{A}_{\text{imp}}$ is freely available in the DIGITAL.CSIC repository in Álvarez et al. (2025b). The RADPROF 2018 to 2023 discrete bottle data is freely available at the OCADS NCEI NOAA repository, through the following link https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/ocean-carbon-acidification-data-system/oceans/RADPROF/RADPROF_Table.html. Access to both data collections and software is welcomed to explore opportunities for collaboration and co-authorship.

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Supporting Information

Additional Supporting Information may be found in the online version of this article.

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